

CONTEMPORARY AGRICULTURE
SAVREMENA POLJOPRIVREDA

The Serbian Journal of Agricultural Sciences
Srpski časopis za poljoprivredne nauke

Vol. 64, No. 1 - 2, Pp. 1 - 119, 2015.

www:Contemporary Agriculture
ISSN: 0350-1205 UDC: 63(497.1)(051)-540.2

UNIVERSITAS STUDIORUM
NEOPLANTENSIS
University of Novi Sad, Serbia

ПРОГНОСТИЧКА ФАКУЛТЕТ
УНИВЕРЗИТЕТ У НОВОМ САДУ
1954
Published by Faculty of Agriculture, Novi Sad

Original scientific paper

UDC: 005.591.1:581.35

OPTIMIZATION OF SPECIFIC α -TOCOPHEROL CONCENTRATIONS FOR *IN VITRO* CULTURES OF BOVINE SPERMATOZOA*

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Summary: This study was designed to assess the dose- and time-dependent *in vitro* effects of α -tocopherol (α -TOC) on bovine spermatozoa during different time periods (Times 0h, 2h, 6h, 12h, 18h, 24h). Semen samples were collected from 20 adult breeding bulls, and diluted in physiological saline solution containing 0.5% ethanol (96%) together with 0, 1, 5, 10, 50, 100, 200, 500, 1000 and 2000 μ M/L of α -TOC. Most α -TOC concentrations had beneficial effects on the spermatozoa motion parameters, while groups supplemented with 500 and 200 μ M/L exhibiting significant differences ($P < 0.05$ and $P < 0.001$, respectively). The MTT assay indicated that none of the α -TOC concentrations had a negative or cytotoxic effect on the spermatozoa mitochondrial activity, and moreover showed a significantly ($P < 0.05$; $P < 0.01$; $P < 0.001$, respectively) improved cell viability in all the experimental groups throughout the *in vitro* culture. The NBT test showed that the addition of 1000-50 μ M/L α -TOC had an instant positive effect on the spermatozoa protection against free radical production. This protection remained present with a significant impact at all timeframes ($P < 0.001$ and $P < 0.01$, respectively). At the same time, all α -TOC concentrations exhibited significant ($P < 0.05$, $P < 0.01$ and $P < 0.001$, respectively) protective effects on the spermatozoa free radical formation during the end-stages of spermatozoa culture. The results indicate that the addition of α -tocopherol, especially in concentrations ranging between 500 and 50 μ M to the culture medium could be beneficial for the overall stimulation of spermatozoa activity and protection against possible *in vitro* oxidative stress development.

Key words: vitamin E, spermatozoa, bulls, motility, viability, superoxide production.

INTRODUCTION

Vitamin E is a term that encompasses a group of potent, lipid-soluble tocol (tocopherol) and to-cotrienol derivatives qualitatively exhibiting the biological activity of RRR- α -tocopherol (Wen and Geffen, 2006). Structural analyses have revealed that molecules having vitamin E antioxidant activity include four tocopherols (α -, β -, γ - and

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*This study was supported by the European Community under the Project no. 26220220180: Building Research Centre „AgroBioTech” and the Scientific Grant Agency of the Ministry of Education of the Slovak Republic VEGA, Project no. 1/0857/14 and Slovak Research and Development Agency, Project no. APVV-0304-12.

δ-) and four tocotrienols (α-, β-, γ- and δ-) that occur naturally differing in the number and position of methyl groups on the chroman ring (Brigelius-Flohe and Traber, 1999).

α-tocopherol (α-TOC) is the most abundant form in nature and mostly available in food (Wen and Geffen, 2006), having the highest biological activity, and reversing vitamin E deficiency symptoms (Brigelius-Flohe and Traber, 1999). The molecular functions fulfilled specifically by α-TOC have yet to be fully described, but it is unlikely they are limited to general antioxidant functions, although the antioxidant feature is the flagship of the biological activity related to vitamin E (Wen and Geffen, 2006).

Vitamin E is present within the seminal plasma and plasma membrane (Agarwal et al., 2003). It is a lipid soluble, chain-breaking antioxidant, able to terminate a free radical chain reaction. Specifically, it inhibits peroxidation of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA), which is especially important in spermatozoa due to their high PUFA content (Bolle et al., 2002). A broad array of studies support the role for α-TOC in reversing the pathogenesis of male infertility. A positive correlation was found between α-TOC extracted from spermatozoa membranes and the percentage of motile, living and morphologically normal sperm cells (BOLLE et al., 2002). Furthermore, α-TOC levels were found to be decreased significantly among oligo- and azoospermic subjects as compared to normospermic controls (Bhardway et al., 2004).

A significant improvement in the *in vitro* ability of spermatozoa to bind the *zona pellucida* of unfertilized oocytes was found in men with high ROS production supplemented with VIT E for 3 months (Kessopoulou et al., 1995). *In vivo* toxicology studies have shown that VIT E has proven to be an efficient in alleviating testicular and epididymal damage as well as disruption of spermatogenesis caused by environmental pollutants or chemotherapeutics (Oda and El-Maddawy, 2012). Moreover, *in vitro* experiments have revealed beneficial and protective effects of the molecule on the cryosurvival for human and animal spermatozoa (Amini-Pour et al., 2013), as well as protection of the male germ cells in environmental with increased ROS-production (O'Flaherty et al., 2006; Bansal and Bilaspury, 2009).

In order to define an optimal concentration of α-TOC for future experiments, this *in vitro* study was aimed to find out the efficacy of different α-TOC concentrations on bovine spermatozoa motility, viability and superoxide radical formation during a 24 hour *in vitro* cultivation.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Bovine semen samples were obtained from 20 adult breeding bulls (Slovak Biological Services, Nitra, Slovak Republic). The samples had to accomplish the basic criteria given for the corresponding breed. The samples were obtained on a regular collection schedule using an artificial vagina. After collecting the samples were stored in the laboratory at room temperature (22–25°C).

Each sample was diluted in physiological saline solution (PS; sodium chloride 0.9 % w/v; Bieffe Medital, Italia) containing 0.5% ethanol (96% ethyl alcohol, EtOH; Merck Chemicals, Darmstadt, Germany), with various concentrations of α-tocopherol (α-TOC; Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, USA; A – 2000; B – 1000; C – 500; D – 200; E – 100; F – 50; G – 10; H – 5; I - 1 μM/L) using a dilution ratio of 1:40. The samples were cultured at room temperature (22–25°C). We compared the control (Ctrl) group (medium without CUR supplementation) with the experimental groups.

Motility and progressive motility analysis was carried out using the CASA (Computer Assisted Semen Analyzer) system equipped with the SpermVision™ program (MiniTub, Tiefenbach, Germany) and the Olympus BX 51 microscope (Olympus, Japan) at cultivation Times 0 h, 2h, 6h (models suitable for a short-term *in vitro* culture) as well as 12 h and 24 h (models suitable for a long-term *in vitro* culture). Each sample was placed into the Makler Counting Chamber (depth 10 μm, Sefi-Medical Instruments, Israel) and the percentage of motile (motility > 5 μm/s; MOT) and progressively motile spermatozoa (motility > 20 μm/s; PROG) was evaluated. 1000–1500 cells were assessed in each analysis (Massányi et al., 2008). Viability of the cells exposed to α-TOC *in vitro* was evaluated by the metabolic activity (MTT) assay (Mosmann, 1983; Knazicka et al., 2012). This colorimetric assay measures the conversion of 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT; Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, USA) to purple formazan particles by mitochondrial succinate dehydrogenase of intact mitochondria of living cells.

Formazan can then be measured spectrophotometrically at a measuring wavelength of 570 nm against 620 nm as reference by a microplate ELISA reader (Multiskan FC, ThermoFisher Scientific, Finland). The data are expressed in percentage of control (i.e. optical density of formazan from cells not exposed to α -TOC). Results from the analysis were collected during five repeated experiments at each concentration.

The nitroblue-tetrazolium (NBT) test was used to assess the intracellular formation of superoxide radical (Esfandiari et al., 2003). This assay is conducted by counting the cells containing blue NBT formazan deposits, which are formed by reduction of the membrane permeable, water-soluble, yellow-colored, nitroblue tetrazolium chloride (2,2'-bis(4-Nitrophenyl)-5,5'-diphenyl-3,3'-(3,3'-dimethoxy-4,4'-diphenylene)ditetrazolium chloride; Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, USA) and superoxide radical. Formazan can be measured spectrophotometrically at a measuring wavelength of 620 nm against 570 nm as reference by a microplate ELISA reader (Multiskan FC, ThermoFisher Scientific, Finland). The data were expressed in percentage of control (i.e. optical density of formazan from cells not exposed to α -TOC). Results from the analysis were collected during five repeated experiments at each concentration (Tvrđá et al., 2013).

Statistical analysis was carried out using the GraphPad Prism program (version 3.02 for Windows; GraphPad Software, La Jolla California USA, www.graphpad.com). Descriptive statistical characteristics (mean, standard error) were evaluated at first. One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's post test was used for statistical evaluations. The level of significance was set at ^A($P<0.001$); ^B($P<0.01$); ^C($P<0.05$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The CASA assessment of the motion parameters showed a gradual decrease of spermatozoa motility and progressive motility in all groups over the course of a 24h *in vitro* culture (Table 1, Table 2). The initial (Time 0h) MOT was higher in all experimental groups when compared to the control group (0 μ M/L α -TOC), although without any statistical significance ($P>0.05$). Although statistically insignificant, a motion-promoting effect of α -TOC remained visible after 2h, specifically in experimental groups C (500 μ M/L α -TOC), D (200 μ M/L α -TOC), E (100 μ M/L α -TOC), F (50 μ M/L α -TOC) and G (10 μ M/L α -TOC). At the same time, 2000 μ M/L α -TOC (group A), 1000 μ M/L α -TOC (group B), 5 μ M/L α -TOC (group H) and 1 μ M/L α -TOC (group I) caused a non-significant decrease of the spermatozoa motility parameters. After 6h, the decline of spermatozoa motion characteristics was significantly ceased in the group C ($P<0.001$) alongside with an insignificant decline ($P>0.05$) in groups A, E and F in comparison with the control. Examination at 12h of *in vitro* culture showed that the spermatozoa motility and progressive motility were significantly increased in the group C ($P<0.001$), together with an insignificant ($P>0.05$) increase in groups B, D, E and F when compared to the control. At the end of the experiments (24h), the highest motility parameters were observed in all experimental groups, being significantly higher in groups C and D in comparison with the control ($P<0.05$) (Table 1, Table 2).

Table 1. Spermatozoa motility (%) in the absence (Ctrl) or presence (A-I) of α -tocopherol during different time periods (Mean \pm SEM; n=20)

	Ctrl	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
0h	90.00 \pm 1.27	86.42 \pm 1.15	90.94 \pm 1.52	93.00 \pm 1.30	92.96 \pm 1.27	88.35 \pm 0.88	89.73 \pm 1.35	88.00 \pm 1.10	85.58 \pm 1.14	88.33 \pm 0.96
2h	89.88 \pm 2.25	85.44 \pm 1.71	87.68 \pm 1.98	90.61 \pm 1.69	87.58 \pm 1.49	87.41 \pm 1.66	87.91 \pm 1.03	89.96 \pm 1.31	83.66 \pm 1.74	83.23 \pm 1.10
6h	80.61 \pm 2.14	78.85 \pm 3.53	78.71 \pm 1.35	88.52 \pm 1.57 ^C	83.75 \pm 1.57	81.02 \pm 1.68	80.96 \pm 1.12	80.59 \pm 1.98	78.19 \pm 1.79	76.49 \pm 1.54
12h	73.78 \pm 2.05	71.47 \pm 1.87	75.00 \pm 1.47	83.82 \pm 1.01 ^A	76.78 \pm 3.02	74.93 \pm 2.04	74.17 \pm 2.44	73.30 \pm 1.87	73.64 \pm 1.64	69.48 \pm 2.90
18h	62.18 \pm 1.98	60.88 \pm 3.14	68.43 \pm 1.90	74.29 \pm 1.53 ^A	69.59 \pm 1.82	67.10 \pm 1.85	65.13 \pm 2.01	64.61 \pm 3.51	63.95 \pm 3.13	60.68 \pm 1.35

24h	53.75±	55.41±	59.62±	62.75±	62.64±	59.10±	59.49±	57.20±	56.33±	54.42±
	1.84	2.67	3.61	2.74 ^A	3.28 ^A	3.02	3.27	3.06	2.61	2.74

^A P<0.001, ^B P<0.01, ^C P<0.05

Table 2. Spermatozoa progressive motility (%) in the absence (Ctrl) or presence (A-I) of α -tocopherol during different time periods (Mean±SEM; n=20)

	Ctrl	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
0h	82.51± 1.38	80.79± 1.38	79.08± 1.63	87.87± 1.25	87.96± 1.38	86.50± 1.44	83.74± 2.22	85.62± 1.49	84.79± 1.30	81.19± 1.61
2h	80.41± 2.21	79.83± 1.74	77.00± 2.70	85.97± 1.72	86.48± 1.62	82.50± 1.58	81.98± 1.13	81.70± 1.41	80.16± 2.10	79.62± 1.21
6h	74.67± 2.13	69.06± 3.45	76.70± 1.39	83.37± 1.62 ^C	80.00± 1.65	77.11± 1.64	75.01± 1.09	72.10± 1.92	69.81± 1.69	67.24± 1.52 ^C
12h	63.98± 1.95	61.84± 1.79	65.06± 1.21	75.94± 1.12 ^A	65.94± 2.82	67.03± 2.08	65.71± 2.39	64.02± 1.72	65.99± 1.68	60.14± 3.06
18h	59.48± 2.07	59.07± 3.01	65.05± 2.02	69.51± 1.43 ^A	66.10± 1.90	63.60± 1.92	62.64± 2.14	58.95± 3.22	55.18± 1.57	57.09± 3.07
24h	50.73± 3.11	46.79± 2.69	51.78± 3.44	54.10± 2.80	52.01± 3.40	51.14± 2.97	50.14± 3.27	45.73± 1.70	39.86± 2.78	44.98± 2.95

^A P<0.001, ^B P<0.01, ^C P<0.05

According to the MTT assay, the immediate α -TOC administration (Time 0h) led to a significant improvement of the sperm cell viability in groups B, C, D and E (P<0.001 in case of C, P<0.05 in case of B, D and E). At 2h it was revealed that all concentrations of α -TOC had a stimulating and vitality-promoting effect on the bovine spermatozoon, alongside with statistically significant results (P<0.001; Figure 1) when compared to the control group (0 μ M/L α -TOC). These beneficial effects remained visible and statistically relevant throughout Time 6h and Time 12h, as shown in Figure 1 (P<0.001 in all experimental groups vs. control). After 18h of *in vitro* culture, the cell viability remained significantly improved in the experimental groups B-D (P<0.05), however the beneficial impact of α -TOC extended through a broader array of concentrations with significant effects at the end of the culture (Time 24h; P<0.05 in case of group A; P<0.01 in case of groups E-H; P<0.001 in case of groups B-D; Figure 1).

The NBT test revealed that concentrations between 1000 and 50 μ M of α -TOC had an instant and significant (P<0.001 in case of groups B-E; P<0.05 in case of group F) protective effect against superoxide production in the sperm cells, when compared to the control (Figure 2). Positive effects of α -TOC remained persistent and significant (P<0.001) over the course 2h, 6h and 12h, and was subsequently joined by the experimental groups G (Time 2h; P<0.01), H (Time 6h; P<0.01) and I (Time 12h; P<0.05). NBT examinations of both representative timeframes (Time 18h and 24h) of a long-term *in vitro* spermatozoa culture showed that all α -TOC concentrations led to a significant improvement in the oxidative balance of the bovine germ cells in comparison with the control (P<0.05 in case of groups A and I; P<0.01 in case of groups B and H; P<0.001 in case of groups C, D, E, F and G; Figure 2).

In the present study, ROS-mediated damage to sperm cell with a subsequent loss of spermatozoa fertilizing potential could be reduced using various doses of α -tocopherol. ROS are generally produced under elevated oxygen tension, which may be induced when spermatozoa are transferred to and manipulated under *in vitro* conditions. Supplementation of antioxidants to semen can protect against the damaging effects of ROS on sperm motility and viability, and therefore may be of clinical value in cryopreservation and assisted reproduction protocols (Baker et al., 1996).

Our results indicate that α -TOC improves the percentage of motile and viable spermatozoa under *in vitro* conditions. It is known that normal *ex vivo* oxidative stress to spermatozoa causes a significant damage to their structural components related to the cell movement, resulting in a reduction in their motility. Nevertheless, supplementing the culture medium with different doses of α -TOC preserved the sperm motility throughout the *in vitro* incubation. Thus, we may suggest that α -TOC is effective in preventing the rapid loss of motility regularly

developing during spermatozoa incubation, thus maintains the motion characteristics under oxidative stress conditions.

This study shows that different doses of α -TOC improve the viability of bovine sperm. These results may be based on the fact that α -TOC protects the spermatozoa by preventing mitochondrial oxidative DNA and membrane damage, thereby helping the spermatozoon to overcome oxidative attacks. Thus, by maintaining the cell integrity and optimal function and activity of spermatozoa, α -TOC improves the per cent of sperm viability. Moreover, supplementing culture media with with α -TOC of variants of vitamin E improved the sperm viability in humans (Askari et al., 1994) and in rabbits (Yousef et al., 2003).

All concentrations of α -TOC significantly reduced the intracellular production of superoxide radical. It may be explained by the fact that α -TOC reduces the oxidative damage and lipid peroxidation in sperm cell membranes by disrupting oxidative chain reactions. Thus, α -TOC increases the sperm membrane integrity and promotes the protection of the spermatozoa against the formation of the superoxide radical, which is considered to be the most reactive ROS initiating further oxidative processes. Similar observations have been reported in humans (Verma and Kanwar, 1999) and boars (Slebozinska et al., 1995).

Figure 1. The effect of various doses of α -tocopherol on the viability of bovine spermatozoa at 0h, 2h, 6h, 12h and 24h. Each bar represents mean (\pm SEM) optical density as the percentage of controls ($n=20$), which symbolize 100%. The data were obtained from five independent experiments. The level of significance was set at ^A $P<0.001$; ^B $P<0.01$; ^C $P<0.05$. Ctrl – 0; A – 2000; B – 1000; C – 500; D – 200; E – 100; F – 50; G – 10; H – 5; I – 1 μ M/L α -TOC.

Figure 2. The effect of various doses of α -tocopherol on the spermatozoa superoxide production at 0h, 2h, 6h, 12h and 24h. Each bar represents mean (\pm SEM) optical density as the percentage of controls ($n=20$), which symbolize 100%. The data were obtained from five independent experiments. The level of significance was set at ^A $P < 0.001$; ^B $P < 0.01$; ^C $P < 0.05$. Ctrl – 0; A – 2000; B – 1000; C – 500; D – 200; E – 100; F – 50; G – 10; H – 5; I – 1 $\mu\text{M/L}$ α -TOC.

The present study shows the effectiveness of α -TOC in protecting spermatozoa motility and viability by decreasing the intracellular ROS production. Comparable events have been observed in experiments with human (Aitken et al., 1989; Agarwal et al., 2007), boar (Slebodzinska et al., 1995) and rabbit (Yousef et al., 2003) spermatozoa.

α -tocopherol has been reported to inhibit the free radical-induced damage to sensitive spermatozoa cell membranes as it is a major chain-breaking antioxidant (Sinclair, 2000). The present results suggest that α -TOC may directly quench various free radicals generated during the *in vitro* generated OS. Thus, by scavenging these radicals, it breaks the chain reaction and forms a relatively stable complex such as the tocopheroxyl radical. Similar suggestions have been made by Verma and Kanwar (1999) in a human model.

CONCLUSION

It may be concluded that all doses of α -tocopherol increased the percentage of motile and viable spermatozoa but decreased and prevented the intracellular overproduction of free radicals within the sperm mitochondrial membrane, although the most effective concentrations of α -tocopherol seem to vary between 500 and 100 μ M/L α -tocopherol seems to protect bovine spermatozoa against the damages caused by reactive oxygen species. Supplementing the semen samples with α -tocopherol could therefore be of scientific importance for extending the time of spermatozoa storage before further designated andrology experiments and clinical procedures, such as artificial insemination, *in vitro* fertilization techniques or spermatozoa cryopreservation.

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OPTIMIZACIJA SPECIFIČNE KONCENTRACIJE α -TOCOPHEROL ZA *IN VITRO* KULTIVACIJU SPERMATOZOIDA BIKA

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Izvod: Istraživanje je izvedeno da se ustanove doze i potrebno vreme za *in vitro* efekt α -tocopherol (α -TOC) na spermatozoide bika, tokom različitih vremenskih perioda (0h, 2h, 6h, 12h, 18h, 24h). Dobijeni rezultati pokazuju da dodavanje α -tocopherola, posebno u koncentracijama od 500 do 50 μ M u medijum za kultivaciju, može biti stimulatивно za aktivnost spermatozoida i njihovu zaštitu protiv mogućih *in vitro* oksidativnih stresnih faktora.

Ključne reči: *vitamin E, spermatozoidi, pokretljivost, produkcija superoxide, bik.*

Received / *Primljen*: 21.11.2014.

Accepted / *Prihvaćen*: 01.12.2014